

HARNESSING GENETIC DIVERSITY: ENHANCING RUST RESISTANCE IN WHEAT LANDRACES FROM CENTRAL ASIA

¹Shamim Khan, ²Niaz Ali, ³Fahim Ullah Khan

¹student, Department of Botany, Hazara University Mansehra Pakistan, ²associate professor, Department of Botany, Hazara University Mansehra Pakistan, ³assistant professor, Department of Agriculture, Hazara University Mansehra Pakistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017079>

Abstract. As global food security faces unprecedented challenges, developing resilient wheat varieties has never been more crucial. This study delves into 74 diverse wheat landraces from Azerbaijan, Iran, Pakistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan, examining their morphological traits, yield potential, and resistance to stripe rust—a formidable threat to wheat crops. Conducted at Hazara University Mansehra, our field assessments revealed significant variability in essential characteristics such as days to heading, plant height, and grain yield. Using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), we discovered that the first two components (PC1 and PC2) captured 48.59% of the total variance. PC1 was primarily associated with grain yield, while PC2 encompassed productive tillers, plant height, and disease resistance. Our cluster analysis further highlighted the distinct genetic diversity among the landraces, categorizing them into several unique groups. In terms of disease resistance, we observed a compelling range from high resistance (0-TR) to susceptibility (CI = 60-80) to stripe rust. Notably, SSR marker analysis of landraces exhibiting a 0-TR response revealed the presence of critical resistance genes: *Yr-05*, *Yr-10*, and *Yr-15*. This discovery deepens our understanding of the genetic mechanisms that underpin disease resistance. This research emphasizes the vital role of the rich germplasm from Central Asia in harnessing a wide array of genetic diversity. By integrating these landraces—particularly those containing essential resistance genes—we can significantly enhance breeding programs aimed at producing high-yielding, rust-resistant wheat varieties. Our findings not only address the pressing food security challenges of tomorrow but also hold the promise of elevating wheat production across Central Asia, making a substantial impact on sustainable agriculture. Join us in exploring the potential of these unique landraces and their indispensable contributions to our agricultural future!

Key words: Wheat landraces; Stripe rust resistance; Genetic diversity; Principal Component Analysis; Food security